

IMPACT OF PRIVACY ON THE MARKETING PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

Hotel sector is encountering a significant number of challenges, especially in terms of marketing performance and customer perception. It is thus crucial that hotel managers consider guest satisfaction when implementing strategies for enhancing product promotion, brand value and marketing performance. Given these considerations, the present paper investigated how marketing performance was influenced by privacy. A sample of managers from Jordanian hotels was used for data collection, with Smart Partial Least Squares being employed for the analysis of the 250 responses received. Based on the findings, marketing performance was favourably influenced by privacy. Hotels and the digital marketing agencies can use such findings to develop a marketing performance and the digital strategies targeting consumers.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitality as a concept is associated with warmth and respect. In some cases, it can even be associated with safety and protection. What is more, hospitality can generate cultural appreciation and understanding (Sharar & Yousef, 2018). Statistics show that Jordan had a population of approximately 9.5million in 2018, which is relatively small. The country shares a border with Israel, Saudi Arabia and Iraq, and is home to various natural resources. Tourism is one of the most important industries in the country, with hoteliers having made a significant contribution of 10%-14% to the national gross domestic product over the last ten years. What is more, this industry employs the most individuals in the private sector and is the second-highest industry bringing in foreign currency (Muhtaseb & Daoud, 2018). Unlike their neighboring countries, Jordan is heavily dependent on external sources for meeting its energy requirements. Moreover, Alshourah et al. (2018) describe the country as being small and

possessing limited natural resources, which makes it extremely susceptible to external distresses. Jordan is ranked 73rd on the Global Competitiveness Index, primarily due to the influx of refugees seeking refuge in the country as a result of the conflict in other countries within the region. Their economic growth fell from an average of 5.4% between 2000–2012 to a mere 1.9% in 2015, which marks a record low (Ghazal, 2018).

Now, the hotel sector is encountering a significant number of challenges, especially in terms of marketing performance and customer perception (Magno, Cassia & Bruni, 2017; Huang, Ho & Chen, 2016; Maroofi, 2015). It is thus crucial that hotel managers consider guest satisfaction when implementing strategies for enhancing product promotion, brand value and marketing performance. Although marketing performance and branding have been recognized as key factors in hotel management, standard operating procedures and market performance in Jordan's star-rated hotels still require substantial development (Shaaban and Ghoneim, 2017).

Tourism is fundamental for the economy, not only in Jordan but throughout the world. Several researchers (Alshourah et al., 2018; Rababah, 2012; Al-Momani and Noor, 2009) have found that the hotel industry in Jordan is fiercely competitive. What's more, Al-Azzam (2016) has pointed out that occupancy rates have been fluctuating and declining in Jordan since 2012. Dissatisfaction amongst hotel guests was one of the key reasons for this decline, which ultimately caused insufficient customer retention and market share, and a significant drop in profitability. In turn, this has generated a decline in marketing performance amongst hotels in Jordan (Al-Adamat, 2015; Al-Laymoun, 2016; Waskito, 2018). What's more, researchers (Talabi, 2015; Al-Adamat, 2015; Yadav & Singh, 2014; and Alshourah et al., 2018) have highlighted the need for Jordanian hotels to enhance their business and marketing performances, as is also the case for hotels in many countries. To achieve this, they must develop and keep the hotels information more secure that might be keep the competitors blind and can't penetrate the information, therefore, the current study aims to

In previous research, marketing performance has been found to be significantly and positively impacted by Mobile CRM. For example, Soliman (2011) identified a positive relationship between CRM and marketing performance. They found that, in financial institutions, marketing performance and Mobile CRM dimensions are positively related. Moreover, both Shaaban and Ghoneim (2017) and Fernando & Karunanithy (2015) found that Mobile CRM significantly influences a company's marketing performance. However, other researchers including Reinartz, Krafft & Hoyer (2004), Ernst (2011) and Nasution (2018) found a negative, non-significant relationship between Mobile CRM and the variables of company performance and marketing performance, which indicates the presence of an oscillating relationship between Mobile CRM and marketing performance. What is more, a number of researchers (Wang & Kim, 2017; Chubing, Shenghao & Na, 2019) have revealed that privacy can improve company performance. Similarly, other researchers have found that privacy can impact and lead to mobile CRM (Zaker, 2017; Marolt et al., 2020). As well, some researchers revealed that the search engine marketing affected the mobile CRM, in the same vein, (000) found that the search engine marketing affected the marketing performance, as well (00000) revealed that the search engine marketing increased and improved the mobile CRM application appearance. Therefore,

the present paper aims to investigate the impact of privacy on marketing performance among Jordanian hotels.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND DEVELOPMENTS OF HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Marketing performance

Bonoma and Clark (1988) argue there may be no other concept in the history of marketing that has been as resistant to development, definition, and application as marketing performance. This may be the research for which researchers in strategic (Chakravarthy, 1986; Morgan and Strong, 2003) and marketing fields (Clark and Ambler, 2001; Morgan et al., 2002; Vorhies and Morgan, 2003) agree that marketing performance is an inherently multidimensional process (Sampaio et al., 2011).

There are several factors involved in analyzing marketing performance, including effectiveness, efficiency, and adaptability. In this regard, efficiency refers to the evaluation of the relationship between marketing inputs and outputs and inputs. Moreover, the key objective of efficiency is maximizing output whilst simultaneously reducing input. The second factor, effectiveness, refers to the expected outcome of marketing initiatives. On the other hand, adaptability can be defined as an assessment of performance based on the company's external setting. A company must adapt to the environment in which it finds itself. This means it is significantly impacted by the actions of competitors and general changes that occur within the company environment, including changes to guidelines, customer preferences and marketing partners (such as suppliers, service companies and distribution channel members). These factors must thus be considered when developing marketing initiatives (Clark, 2000).

In recent years, several different measures to assess company performance have been put forward. These range from financial measures (e.g., sales growth, revenues, etc.) to non-financial measures (such as market share, customer satisfaction, customer retention, customer loyalty, adaptability, and brand equity). Moreover, they can be one-dimensional or multi-dimensional (effectiveness, efficiency, marketing audits, marketing assessments, marketing implementation, etc.) (Ambler, Kokkinaki & Puntoni, 2004; Clark, 1999). In this research, the following factors will be used to assess company performance, as recommended by (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2021): customer retention, customer satisfaction and company market share. All dimensions measured in this research are interrelated. In other words, any changes in one will lead to changes in another. All such factors are vital in assessing marketing performance in the hotel industry, as satisfied customers are likely to return and use the same company again. Thus, company profits will increase, and this will ultimately increase the company's market share.

Previous studies investigating CRM have shown that companies that use CRM achieve better performance (Boateng, 2014). Moreover, it has been found that customers are more loyal to a company if they have a strong relationship with them. They are also more likely to remain in a mutually beneficial relationship (Henczel, 2016). It was revealed by Benedettini, Swink & Neely (2017) that loyal customers are happy to purchase the products from the same company

repeatedly. Additionally, Qasem and Abukhadijeh (2016) investigated the effects that CRM had on customer retention and market share for bank customers in Jordan. Similarly, Nasution & Rafiki (2018) revealed a negative correlation between CRM and company performance through top management support, and between CRM implementation and customer retention. Rodriguez & Boyer (2020) and Soliman (2011) and Al-Bakri (2014) highlighted that the mobile CRM and CRM implementation positively influenced the marketing performance. However, neither Bustami (2016) was able to find a significant relationship between mobile CRM and company performance. Nonetheless, several researchers, including Soliman (2011) have found that CRM and marketing performance are significantly and positively related. Moreover, Kim et al. (2016) also found that mobile CRM affects a company's marketing performance. As a result, criteria for marketing performance and growth have been established. Research conducted by Dursun & Çelik (2018) also found that mobile CRM positively affects marketing performance. The following hypothesis has thus been developed in the present work, based on the findings of prior research

2.2 Privacy

Privacy has been recognized as one basic attribute of website quality by almost every study. Privacy is the degree to which the website has adequate security features to protect user information as well the organization information, and facilitate a safe transaction between the organization employees especially regarding the information concerning the marketing strategies, likewise the transactions between sellers and buyers, hence increasing the trust in the organization system then increasing the market share (Wolfenbarger and Gilly 2003). It is challenging to maintain a safe online marketplace as the online market is characteristic of low entry costs for various traders to participate in the e-commerce, lack of the ability for buyers to examine the product and evaluate the seller, few secure payment options for the transactions, and lack of direct encounter between buyers and sellers in the transaction process. Therefore, the assurance of privacy and security can reduce customer anxiety, foster trust, and contribute to positive evaluation of the transaction value (Xiao, 2016). In the relationship between privacy and marketing performance. Maintz & Zaumseil (2019) and Al-Habil et al. (2017) revealed the indicated that the level of availability of (privacy, credibility, efficiency of service providers, tact, empathy, reliability, communication, accessibility, material and human aspects, response level) increasing the marketing performance. The following hypothesis has thus been developed in the present work, based on the findings of prior research

H1: Privacy positively impacts marketing performance

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Method

Relevant studies were consulted in order to extract the research parameters. Thus, privacy (PR) comprised four items based on the uni-dimensionality model proposed by (Xiao, 2016); Search engine marketing comprised five items based on the uni-dimensionality model proposed by (Bhandari, R. S., & Bansal, 2018); marketing performance (MP) and comprised four

subsections; customer satisfaction with five items; , customer retention with five items; , market share with five items; , and profitability with five items; which were adapted from. A five-point Likert scale was employed for the measurement of every parameter. Furthermore, in line with the recommendation by Tehseen, Ramayah and Sajilan (2017), the independent and dependent variables were derived from distinct sources so as to avoid the problem of common method variance (CMV).as for the pre-test of the questionnaire After having prepared the measurement items and prior to the main data collection, it is necessary to test the validity of the questionnaire in order to ensure that it would be effective in terms of exactly measuring what it was supposed to measure. Therefore, the current study conducted two phases of pre-testing, with these being the first phase that was conducted between August and October2021, which involved asking an expert panel of three academicians to assess the questionnaire. The questionnaire was reviewed by these three experts, and their comments were taken into consideration. The next phase ofpre-testing, as mentioned by (Akroush, Al-Mohammad and Odetallah, 2015), was conducting the pilot test through the interviewing of a small population size that is appropriate and adequate. For this study, we pre-tested the questionnaire through interviews with 30 respondents, who were managers that represented 30 tourism restaurants operating in Jordan in Jordan. This was carried out to ensure that the questions in the study instrument were adequate, good, clear, reasonable, and understood in relation to the purpose of the study.

3.2 Sampling

The back-translation process was constructed in order to translate the questionnaire to Arabic and then return it to English, because the English language is not used as an official language in Jordan (Brislin, 1970). This was carried out in order to ensure that it would be well understood by the respondents. Online self-administered survey was employed targeting managers and employees of tourism restaurants operating in Jordan, which could be accessed through a link that was distributed through emails. Furthermore, participants were asked to send the link on to acquaintances. Since the purpose of the work was to assess the validity of theoretical effects, purposefully sampling was adopted as it was considered to be a suitable sampling approach (Ngah et al., 2020). The smallest number of participants was established by conducting power analysis. This number depends on how complex the model is. In this way, a minimum sample of 85 was obtained as the medium effect size based on the three research predictors had a power of 0.8 (Gefen et al., 2011). According to the result of power analysis, a sample of 300 participants was chosen to ensure that as many responses as possible were attained.

3.3 Data Analysis

Two software programs were used in the data analysis: SPSS-23 and PLS-SEM version 3.3.6. First, descriptive statistics were used to determine the response rate, the demographic profile of the respondents, and the response bias. The PLS-SEM software was used to obtain inferential statistics in order to test for outliers, and to assess the measurement model and the structural model. The reasons for using PLS were to analyze the study framework: PLS-SEM has been reported to account for measurement errors, and can yield better estimates of

mediating effects. It is also more beneficial to use PLS when researchers are faced with complex models, as the PLS software handles non-normal data well.

Result

A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 260 were returned from the tourism restaurants operating in Jordan; this represents a response rate of 86.6%. However, 10 questionnaires were invalid because they were incomplete, giving a final total of 250 valid questionnaires.

Measurement Model

Table 1 shows the initial standardized factor loadings of the model items ranging from 0.727 to 0.953; hence, they were all greater than the suggested threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). The table also shows that the AVE values ranging from 0.630 to 0.780; they were, therefore, all higher than the recommended threshold value of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2019). In addition, the CR values were also more than the recommended threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019), as they ranged from 0.872 to 0.947. Finally, the Cronbach's alpha values ranged from 0.803 to 0.957, so they were greater than the 0.7 threshold value recommended by (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha and Convergent Validity Results for the Model

Construct/ Order	First	Item	factor loading	CR	AVE	Cronbach's alpha
privacy (PR)		PR 1	0.839	0.904	0.702	0.858
		PR 2	0.870			
		PR 3	0.847			
		PR 4	0.792			
Profitability (PRF)		PRF1	0.844	0.932	0.733	0.909
		PRF2	0.859			
		PRF3	0.854			
		PRF4	0.872			
		PRF5	0.851			
Market share (MKS)		MKS1	0.862	0.925	0.711	0.898
		MKS2	0.873			
		MKS3	0.857			
		MKS4	0.856			
		MKS5	0.764			
Customer retention (CSR)		CSR1	0.825	0.923	0.705	0.895
		CSR2	0.823			
		CSR3	0.858			
		CSR4	0.841			
		CSR5	0.850			
Customer satisfaction (CSS)		CSS1	0.816	0.922	0.702	0.894
		CSS2	0.829			
		CSS3	0.851			

	CSS4	0.879			
	CSS5	0.813			
Construct / Second Order	Item	factor loading	CR	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
Marketing performance (MP)	Profitability	0.861	0.910	0.718	0.949
	Satisfaction	0.875			
	Market share	0.758			
	Customer retention	0.889			

Discriminant Validity

In order to measure the discriminant validity, the current study found out the HTMT for the overall model, including mobile CRM, search engine marketing, privacy, marketing performance. Table 4 describes all the HTMT values of the latent constructs in the overall model variables ranged from 0.080 to 0.821, and were thus below the threshold value of 0.90. This result proved that each latent construct measurement was totally discriminatory.

Table 2: HTMT Results

	PR	MP
PR		
MP	0.572	

Assessment of the Structural Model

Direct Effects of the Variables

In the current study, the PLS technique and bootstrapping were used to estimate the structural model with 1000 replications in order to investigate the study hypotheses. This involved five sets of tests to evaluate the R², F², Q², GoF, VIF, and p-value of the inner model (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 3: Testing direct relationships

	Path	St, β	St. d	R²	F²	VIF	T-value	P-value
H3	PR>MP	0.318	0.103	0.477	0.465	2.136	3.087	0.002

In terms of direct linkages, the structural model (Table 3) shows that H1 focused on the influence of privacy on marketing performance was also explored. The following conclusion about the influence of privacy on marketing performance were gathered from the H1 study: T-value of 3.087, St, B 0.318, and p-value of 0.002 (one-tailed). Since the R² value connected with marketing performance was calculated to be 0.477 (Table 3), the findings accounted for roughly 47.7% of the difference in marketing performance, which was consistent with Chin (1998) recommended threshold value of 0.19, the models as a whole goodness of fit and statistical relevant are adequate, with the VIF significance linked with inner being 2.136, respectively, with donations not surpassing 5(Hair et al., 2017), Table 3 shows the results of the direct effect, which reveal that H1, was supported.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5. Discussion

The hotel sector is encountering a significant number of challenges, especially in terms of marketing performance and customer perception. It is thus crucial that hotel managers consider guest satisfaction when implementing strategies for enhancing product promotion, brand value and marketing performance. Although marketing performance and branding have been recognized as key factors in hotel management, standard operating procedures and market performance in Jordan's star-rated hotels still require substantial development. In relation to this objective, the first hypothesis (H1) was formulated, namely, the impact of privacy on marketing performance. The result revealed that the privacy positively affected the marketing performance, if the website or any technology has adequate security features to protect user-information as well the organization information, and facilitate a safe transaction between the organization's employees, especially regarding the information concerning the marketing strategies, and the safety in the transactions between sellers and buyers, thus, increasing the trust in the organization system then increasing the market share, hence increase the marketing performance.

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